

Documentation for Lifestyle Entities Annotation

Annotation scope

The scope of this annotation is to detect lifestyle factor named entities in text. Below are some general examples of the guidelines that will be used in the annotation.

Definition for Lifestyle (LSF):

Lifestyle is a complex and multifaceted concept that involves many different factors. It can be defined as the behaviors, habits, and daily activities that individuals engage in, which can impact their health and well-being. Within the context of lifestyle, there are several categories that can be distinguished and annotated, including:

1. **Beauty and cleaning practices:** Activities related to “hygiene” (e.g. “shower daily”), “use of cosmetic and cleaning products” as well as invasive procedures that people undergo to improve their appearance, such as “cosmetic surgery”.
2. **Nutrition:** Covers different branches including “Dietary habits”, “Food groups”, “Food processing and preparation”, “Macronutrients”, and “Micronutrients”.
3. **Drugs:** Refers to illicit/recreational drugs, not those prescribed by doctors for medical conditions.
4. **Environmental exposures:** Exposure to various environmental factors, such as air pollution, water quality, and workplace hazards, that can impact an individual’s health.
5. **Non-physical leisure time activities:** Any activity an individual might be preoccupied with in their free time that is not a physical activity, e.g. listening to music, and reading books.
6. **Physical activities:** Regular exercise and physical activities including leisure time physical activities, occupational activities, and household activities.
7. **Sleep:** Covers sleep quality, stages, conditions, and sleep habits.
8. **Socioeconomic factors:** Refer to the social and economic conditions including: ‘Income and wealth’, ‘Education’, ‘Occupation’, ‘Housing’, and ‘Social support’.
9. **Mental health practices:** The behaviors and habits related to maintaining good mental health and emotional well-being including “Meditation”, and “psychotherapy”.

General guidelines

- Annotations should be made according to the annotator's best understanding of the **author's intended meaning in context**. In context in this case is the entire abstract that the annotator has to annotate each time. The attribute "LSF out of context" has been added for cases where the annotators judge that a term can appear as an LSF in text, but the intended meaning in context is not that of a Lifestyle factor.
- For a **Lifestyle_factor** the following attributes can be selected (None of them, only one, or more if applicable)
 - Beauty and Cleaning
 - Nutrition
 - Drugs
 - Environmental exposures
 - Non physical leisure time activities
 - Physical activity
 - Sleep
 - Socioeconomic factors
 - Mental health practices

What to annotate:

There are two levels in the annotation process that the annotators should keep in mind. The first level is defining which terms to annotate and in which class they potentially belong too, so annotating an LSF named entity and deciding on which branch it belongs to, to add the proper attribute. The second level is which ones appear as LSFs in context and deciding whether the "**LSF out of context**" attribute should be added as well.

- If an LSF is a part of non-LSF entity (e.g. *substance abuse* in **substance abuse disorder** or *chicken* in **chicken embryo** or *tobacco* in **tobacco industry**), it should be annotated as LSF with the attribute: "LSF out of context".
- Top-level terms (e.g. nutrition) should be annotated.
- Standalone adjectives that are not part of named entities should not be annotated (e.g. nutritional, occupational etc).
- Chemical terms should be annotated as standalone entities, and "exposure" is not necessarily annotated as part of these named entities.
- Lifestyle factor names are annotated when they are part of hyphenated compound words (e.g. sleep-related) but NOT when they appear as a substring in a word not separated by a boundary such as a hyphen (e.g. asthmatic)
- Abbreviations are marked if the abbreviation stands for an LSF mention in scope of the annotation, but not if the full form merely includes an entity mention (e.g. in modifier position). For example, the F and D in FDA is not annotated despite it standing for food and drug.).
- Abbreviations should be annotated in all instances that they appear in a document
- Pregnancy, menopause and puberty are not annotated as LSFs.

- Chemicals should be annotated as LSF if they are common, or directly available for ingest as food/supplement, or exposure (even indirect). Examples:
 - sugar intake
 - concentrations of Vitamins A
 - Vitamin D supplements
 - serum Vitamin D levels
 - dioxins
- Chemicals should NOT be annotated as LSF if they are normally metabolized in the body. Examples:
 - HDL-cholesterol concentrations
 - serum Vitamin D 25-OH levels
 - fasting glucose
- Score/index score/index related to LSF can be annotated as LSF. Examples:
 - sleep quality score
- Do not annotate treatments as LSFs. The only form of treatment that is annotated is psychotherapy and entities related to it (e.g., CBT therapy) or treatments with a cosmetic effect (e.g. liposuction).
- Food names should be annotated only if the common taxonomic names (e.g. banana) are actual foods. The Linnean names (e.g. *Citrus sinensis*) should not be annotated.
- Sports and doing sports should generally be annotated and the attribute should be decided case-by-case.
- Different carcinogens should be annotated as Lifestyle Factors (e.g. “exposure to exhaust fumes”).
- The actual word “carcinogen” should not be annotated.
- If an LSF is a part of another LSF, the left-longest match should be annotated
- *Energy content* is a synonym for *caloric intake* and should be annotated as **LSF**
- Terms like **comment toxicity**, **insult**, **threat**, and **identity attack** are considered as LSFs in this annotation effort, as they are forms of **bullying** which is a **Socioeconomic factor** (describes interpersonal relationships)
- social media should be annotated as LSFs when they appear as standalone entities with a tag “**Non physical leisure time activities** “, e.g. *Twitter*, but if they are not referring to the usage of these and the potential effect on human health (i.e. they are not discussed as LSFs), then they should receive an “LSF out of context” attribute.
- Entities that have an “**LSF out of context**” attribute and an “**Environmental exposures**”, “**Non physical leisure time activities**” or “**Physical activity** “ attribute will be removed from the final annotated corpus, as they are not expected to constitute LSFs on their own right. Specifically, “**Non physical leisure time activities**” and “**Physical activity** “ need an action to happen or at least be implied to be considered as Lifestyle Factors (e.g. **internet** on each own is not an LSF, but **internet use** is), while “**Environmental exposures**” are only LSFs, if one is exposed to them, not necessarily as standalone entities (e.g. **acrylamide exposure** is an LSF, but not **acrylamide**).

- work: is problematic because it is a verb, on top of a noun and should only be annotated when it is an LSF in context
- Same rule should be applied to other words that are different parts of speech, when the most common instances are not LSFs.
- standalone “therapy” should be annotated with caution, as so that pharmaceutical therapies are not annotated. If in the abstract therapy refers to “psychotherapy” it should be annotated, with annotator’s note: “Psychotherapy”
- standalone “therapist” should not be annotated.
- relationships standalone follow the same rule as therapy. They will be annotated as “social relationships” with a note. But the word relationship (singular) should be annotated with extra caution (similarly to word work), because it can be part of the phrase “in relationship with” when comparing two things, and there it should not be annotated.
- demographic factors should not be annotated (i.e. age group, gender, and race)
- “beliefs” should not be annotated as LSF, unless it is religious beliefs
- orthodontic practice and orthodontic treatment should be annotated as LSFs
- mark discontinuous entities with add fragment functionality.
- Countries and cities should be annotated by selecting “Geographical Feature” as the attribute.
- Nationalities should not be annotated.
- Occupations should be annotated by selecting “Occupations” as the attribute.

For information on Annodoc, see <http://spyysalo.github.io/annodoc/>.